

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

STRUCTURAL COMPOSITION AND SPECIES DIVERSITY OF THE MICROBIOTA FORMED IN THE ORAL CAVITY

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Abstract

The presented work is dedicated to the study of the structural composition and species diversity of the microbiota formed in the oral cavity of the human body. It was found that 35 species of bacteria belonging to 11 genera are living in the oral cavity. It was determined that *Streptococcus* (9 species), *Proteus* (7 species), *Klebsiella* (4 species) and *Treponema* (4 species) genera in the oral cavity have a wide variety of species and make up 68.5% of the formed microbiota. Also, it has been known that the abundance of substances of organic origin in the oral cavity, the presence of an optimal temperature regime and a weak alkaline environment are the basis for the settlement and spread of bacteria with a wide variety of species.

Keywords: human body, oral cavity, microbiota, structural composition, species diversity, bacteria.

In a living organism, the oral cavity and the organs located there perform functional activities and play an important role in human life. Thus, it is through the oral cavity and the organs located there that the human receives food, soaks it in the oral cavity, breaks it down, and thus the first stage of the digestive process begins. It is known that the ingested food is not subjected to any sterilization process and brings non-pathogenic, conditionally pathogenic, pathogenic, toxigenic, etc. to the oral cavity migration of microorganisms. The conducted clinical studies show that these microorganisms are the causative agents of various diseases and after a certain period of time lead to the manifestation of one or another pathology in the oral cavity or internal organs.[5;9;12]. It should be noted that the microbiota formed in the oral cavity of adults is richer in its composition. Because adults eat several times a day, unlike children. This doesn't raise any doubts about the entry of numerous microorganisms into the oral cavity with food. In addition, microorganisms enter the oral cavity both through drinking water and through the air inhaled during the breathing process, respectively [3;4;11]. This makes the microbiota formed in the oral cavity unstable in terms of both number and species diversity. From this point of view, the research conducted in this direction always maintains its relevance.

The aim of the presented work was to study the gender composition and species diversity of the microbiota formed in the oral cavity from a dental point of view.

Material and methods

Clinical materials taken from the oral cavity of patients who came to the Stomatological Polyclinic of Azerbaijan Medical University were used as the research object. The collected samples were planted in meat-peptone broth. At this time, 0.1% casein hydrolyzate was also added to the broth. During the course of

the research, in all cases, the planting material was washed with 0.15M NaCl solution and phosphate-buffer solution was added to the nutrient medium. At this time, the standard optical density unit is 0.05-0.10, the acidity index is pH 7.4-7.6, and the initial planting material with 1000 microbial cells in 1 ml of medium is prepared based on the Paterson-Cook method. Planting material was inoculated for 2 days at a temperature of 20C. After the exposure period is over, the taxonomic affiliation of the bacteria is determined using known determinants based on cultural, morphological and physiological characteristics [1;2;6;8;10].

Results obtained and their discussion.

Among the organs belonging to the human body, the oral cavity is considered the most favorable environment for the settlement of microorganisms. Because the oral cavity has a sufficient amount of protein, carbohydrate, fat, lipid and other organic substances rich in food residues, an optimal temperature regime and a weak alkaline environment. That is why it was determined that there are 35 species of bacteria belonging to 11 genera in the oral cavity (table 1). As can be seen from the table, within the bacterial biota, the genus streptococcus is represented by the most species diversity, which is equal to 25.7% of the total microbiota. The genus proteus also has a fairly wide species diversity (7 species), they make up 20% of the total microbiota. Also, *Klebsiella* and *Treponema* genera are present in bacterial biota with 4 species each or 11.1% staphylococcus genus with 3 species or 8.6%. Inherited genera are characterized by 1 or 2 species within the mycobiota. It was found that the genera *Streptococcus*, *Proteus*, *Klebsiella* and *Treponema* make up more than half of the total microbiota, i.e. 68.5%.

It has been determined that the bacteria spread in the oral cavity mainly live in the soft mucous membrane of the mouth, in the throats of the teeth and in the

intermediate part of the adjacent teeth. It should be noted that although it is easier for bacteria to settle in the mucous membrane of the oral cavity, their localization in the throats, especially between the teeth, takes some time. Because the dental layer of the teeth is made up of quite solid seeds due to its chemical composition. It has been known that the dentine substance of teeth consists of up to 70% of mineral substances, 20% of proteins and 10% of carbohydrates, lipids, etc. composed of compounds of organic origin. At the same time, it was also known that the surface of the teeth in the oral cavity is covered with a soft layer of enamel. The enamel layer consists of up to 80% of protein-

bound water, up to 20% of glycoproteins, and up to 1-2% of potassium, sodium, fluoride etc. consist of ingredients. As it can be seen, in the oral cavity, either the soft mucous membrane, the enamel layer with an amorphous structure, or the hard dentine tissue has a sufficiently rich organic and inorganic substance content. Also, take into account that there are relatively stable hydrothermal conditions in the oral cavity, then there is no doubt about the settlement of bacteria and active vitality. In our opinion, that is why the bacteria living in the oral cavity are characterized by a wide variety of species.

Table 1.

Structural organization and species diversity of the microbiota formed in the oral cavity		
№	Genus bacteria	Species bacteria
1	Bacterioides (1/2)	Bacterioides flagilis; B.melaninogenicus
2	Corynebacterium (1/1)	Corynebacterium diphtheriae
3	Fusobacterium (1/1)	Fusobacterium plauti
4	Enterococcus (1/2)	Enterococcus faecalis; E.faecium
5	Escherichia (1/1)	Escherichia coli
6	Klebsiella (1/4)	Klebsiella planticola; K.ozanae; K.rhinoscheromatis; K.terrigena
7	Staphylococcus (1/3)	Staphylococcus aureus; St.epidermidis; St.phyticus
8	Streptococcus (1/9)	Streptococcus anginosus; Str.faecalis; Str.equisimilis; Str.lactis; Str.mitis; Str.mutans; Str.sanguis; Str.salivarius; Str.pyogenes
9	Treponema (1/4)	Treponema buccalis; T.denticola; T.macrodentium; T.vincentii
10	Proteus (1/7)	Proteus marganii; P.mirabilis; P.myxofaciens; P.inconstans; P.pennera; P.rettgeri; P.vulgaris
11	Veillonella (1/1)	Veillonella parvula

In addition, it was found that a number of representatives of the bacterial biota can be localized in almost all infrastructure elements in the oral cavity. Examples of these include str.salivarius, str.mitis, str.faecalis, str.sanguis, T.vincentii, Veillonella parvula, Fusobacterium plauti, Bacterioides melaninogenicus, Corynebacterium diphtheriae, etc. From the genus streptococcus can be shown. Apparently, bacteria belonging to the genera Streptococcus and Treponema are found throughout the oral cavity, with more species than others. This indicates that the mentioned bacteria have a balanced enzyme system.

In general, the study of each of the constituent elements of the microbiota formed in the oral cavity, both from the dental and bacteriological aspects, is a very important issue and makes researches in this direction relevant.

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